

Deep mapping in digital literary studies – polish experience

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The concept of "deep mapping," i.e. mapping based on close reading of source text (including literary text) and deep interpretation of data, often topographically non-obvious, has been increasingly reflected in recent years in the theory and practice of humanities, including in digital humanities. In this short paper we want to present the Polish experience in this matter. This seems valuable to us because of the value and originality of the research to date, combined with the fact that almost all important research projects (both traditional and digital) do not have an English version so far. Other important reasons are related to digital realizations. First, we want to focus on the case of digital mapping of Warsaw, which is a particularly difficult city in this regard. During the past 200 years, not only the names of Warsaw streets have changed more than once, but also their course. There have even been situations, in the case of historically important streets (such as Nalewki), when a street after World War II bore the same name, but ran in a completely different place. This makes it difficult or even impossible to use geolocation in digital mapping of historic Warsaw. Thus, digital mapping of historic Warsaw - how we try to do it - can be an important case study for other projects. Secondly, our team's work on maps in the digital environment so far has consisted of intensive collaboration between literary researchers, a graphic designer and a cartographer. Showing this way of working just now at a conference on collaboration in the digital environment seems valuable to us.

As a case study, we would like to present our own project, completed in 2019 and currently continuing (as of fall 2022) Atlas of Holocaust Literature - Warsaw Ghetto (. It combines all the key points outlined above - it relies on close reading and deep interpretation of testimonies related to the Warsaw Ghetto and maps the topographically difficult city that is historic Warsaw. The readings' objectives and the difficulties involved in mapping historic Warsaw required adopting - or even finding - non-obvious solutions (including designing cartographic signatures specifically for this project), which involved close collaboration between researchers, a graphic designer and a cartographer. Also, the assumptions made during the reading seem original compared to other deep mapping practices.

Proposed order of presentation:

1) The current state of research and theory on literary topography in Poland (Marta Zielińska, Dorota Siwicka, Elżbieta Rybicka, among others).

2) Mapping historical Warsaw as a challenge for digital humanities.

2 a) Earlier attempts to transfer topographic research to the digital environment (digital maps as an appendix to the book project "Writers' Warsaw" of the Urban Studies Workshop of IKP UW).

3) Digital-born project: Atlas of the Literature of the Holocaust (New Panorama of Polish Literature of the IBL PAN, project manager: Jacek Leociak) as a case study.

4) Assumptions of work on source texts

- close reading

- test selection criteria

- categories of data classification.

5) Functions of a digital map

- map as verification of data

- mapping the narrative of testimony

- map as a story

- combination of form and content

- tool and effect of research and visual representation of processes

6) Stages of mapping | COOPERATION

- interdisciplinary collaboration of researchers from different fields: mainly digital humanities, Holocaust studies and cartography

- cooperation of researchers with the digital team

- cooperation of researchers and graphic designer with cartographer

- cartographic basis: reliable compilation of historical maps and archival data

- joint creation of the map (literature topographer and graphic designer as co-authors)

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